

Using “Nearpod” to Enhance Science Performance of Ninth-Grade Students in Qatar Schools during COVID-19 Pandemic

Hanan Abdulrahman
Arieg Rasmi Ibrahim Merie
Asmaa Baker Guerzoni

Abstract:- The COVID-19 pandemic significantly impacted the education sector, forcing most students to adopt an online learning approach. Various institutions globally use different online learning platforms. Qatar was among the countries that recorded a significant shift to online learning. Nearpod was one of the online learning tools used during the period owing to the growing evidence of its effectiveness. However, there was limited on its effectiveness in middle and high school and the role it plays in enhancing online teaching. This study, therefore, evaluated the impact of Nearpod on the science performance of grade nine students, student's perception of the tools and its ability to foster online teaching. A mixed method research was used to gather quantitative data on student performance before and after using Nearpod as a learning tool, while qualitative data was gathered through surveys administered to the students before and after the intervention. Additionally, science teachers and students were interviewed to assess their views about the tool. The study reported a 5.85% added value after using Nearpod, which suggests that the tool can improve academic performance. Most students acknowledged that Nearpod was more interactive in learning and promoted active learning. The instructors noted its ability to foster teaching by providing resources such as reading tools. Therefore, this study confirms the importance of Nearpod as a learning tool and its benefit in online teaching for science teachers.

Keywords:- Nearpod, performance, active learning, COVID-19, Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the onset of the pandemic over the past two years, the educational sector faced many challenges, with most of the challenges impeding the efforts to introduce online and blended learning in schools. According to UNESCO, more than 50% of students globally were severely affected, with more than 160 countries closing their education systems, affecting more than 87% of students globally (UNESCO, 2020). Like most countries, Qatar invested in technological infrastructure in readiness to support online learning in public

institutions and introduced video-recorded sessions for all subjects in K-12 grade levels (Chaaban et al., 2021). Science educators struggled to find teaching options to improve student's knowledge and research competencies. Consequently, there were significant changes in the quality of learning environments as teachers and students strived to use the resources and maximize what was available (Zheng et al., 2021). Some notable changes in the learning environment include live lessons, e-learning instructions, and interactive platforms to interact with the students (Li & Pei, 2023).

Regardless, all these were not equivalent to face-to-face learning, and most teachers were ill-prepared for the pandemic, while a significant percentage of the students could not effectively use the technological resources. The challenges led to a significant decline in student K-12 student performance. As such, the education sector encouraged students and teachers to learn various technical resources and use the most compatible technology. “Nearpod” is one of the technologies science teachers use to teach scientific concepts during the pandemic. Although the technology is widely used in Qatar, there is limited evidence of its ability to improve performance and enhance the teaching experience. Besides, most studies assessing the effectiveness of Nearpod focused on elementary and higher learning institutions, leaving a gap in its value in middle and high school education. Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate Nearpod's ability to boost science performance among grade nine students and its effectiveness in enhancing teaching instructions.

II. METHODOLOGY

➤ Research Design

The study was conducted using an action plan approach to investigate points to recognize issues affecting students and science teachers, followed by a plan to implement the most viable solution. The model uses a four-staged cyclical approach that includes reflecting, arranging, acting and observing phases (Figure 1). After this, the research progresses to the next cycle with similar stages. A mixed-method approach was also used for the study.

Fig 1: A diagrammatic representation of the action plan model, including the reflecting, arranging, and acting and observational phases.

➤ *Study Population and Sampling*

The study targeted grade 9 learners in a government school in Qatar. Convenience sampling was used to recruit participants for the study. The students were included in the study only if they could independently use different technologies to solve scientific problems. Therefore, the selection was based on the student’s availability and readiness (Taherdoost, 2016).

➤ *Data Collection*

A mixed-method approach was used to gather qualitative and quantitative data on using Nearpod as an interactive learning platform for grade 9 students. The qualitative design was used to identify the perception of individual groups on using the platform, while the quantitative approach was used to compare performance before and after implementing the action plan model (Wong, 2014).

• *Qualitative Phase*

An 8-itemized questionnaire was designed by the researchers and administered to grade nine learners in a governmental school to analyze their opinions towards the

“Nearpod” after the given activity. The Likert scale questionnaire contained five scales, each representing a level to scale their learning experience before and after using the “Nearpod” platform. These scales were: I strongly agree (5), I agree (4), neutral (3), I do not agree (2), and I strongly do not agree (1). A pilot survey was done using 10 grade nine students from a different government school before being administered to the participants. The initial survey was also done to test the test-retest reliability of the questionnaire to improve the quality of the data collected. In each phase of qualitative data collection, the researchers gave face-to-face instructions on answering the questions. The researchers also assisted the students in understanding any unclear questions without influencing their decisions. Each questionnaire was administered for 15-25 minutes, depending on the students’ speed. The researchers also interviewed the participants at the end of the study period. The semi-structured interviews were administered independently to each student for approximately 15 minutes. The interview data was recorded in a notebook and a tape recorder.

• *Qualitative Phase*

The quantitative data was collected in two phases. The first phase collected baseline data by assessing 8 questions on the mirrors unit. The pre-test evaluated the student’s understanding of the unit before using the Nearpod tool. The researchers marked the student’s achievement, and each score was converted to percentages. The assessment was followed by a Likert questionnaire described in section 3.2.1. In the second phase, the sample population was taught using the Nearpod tool and observed their reaction when using it. The students were trained for 2 weeks. Finally, the students were given a standardized 8-question assessment after the Nearpod training. The student’s performance in the last session was also converted into percentages. The pre-test and the post-test assessment sessions lasted for 30 minutes each. The qualitative and quantitative protocols used and timelines are outlined in Table 1. The pre-and post-tests were designed based on the curriculum standards of science subjects for grade nine in Qatar and reviewed by a science coordinator.

Table 1 summarizes the activities and timelines used to gather quantitative and qualitative data from the participants.

TIMELINE	ACTIONS
DIAGNOSTIC STAGE WEEK 1 (5 TH OCT)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pre-test: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Give students a standardized test of eight questions about the Unit “mirrors”. • Give the targeted students a workshop about “How to use the online “Nearpod”. • Observe and reflect on the student’s performance through the collected data from the pr-test.
ACTION STAGE WEEK 2-3 (10 TH OCT)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include the “Nearpod” in the class activities for teaching science. • Observe the students’ interactions in the platform “Nearpod”. • Observe and reflect on the student’s performance.
OBSERVATION STAGE WEEK 4 (31 ST OCT)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post-test: Give students a standardized test of eight questions about the Unit “mirrors”. • Give students a Likert Questionnaire to get their opinion about using the platform “Nearpod”. • Observe and reflect on the student’s performance through the collected data from the test.

➤ *Reliability and Validity Testing*

The test-retest reliability of the questionnaires and the interview was done by administering the two tools to a different set of grade 9 students in a different school. The high reliability of the tools confirmed their ability to collect quality data. A triangulation model was used to prove the validity of the research instruments. The pre-and post-tests were reviewed and approved by a third party (the science coordinator). Further, the questionnaire and the interview questions were also sent to an arbitrator to measure their validity.

➤ *Data Analysis*

A descriptive analytical approach was used in this study to analyze, interpret, and describe the learner's result in the pre and post-test, which aimed to measure the change in student performance before and after using “Nearpod” to teach science subjects. The results of the students’ questionnaire, “The Likert scale,” were analyzed through the Excel program, while thematic analysis was used to analyze the results of the teacher’s interviews. For the interviews, the three researchers independently transcribed the information in the tape recorder, and the findings were compared at the end of the analysis. Any discrepancies in the transcriptions were cleared by the fourth researcher.

➤ *Ethical Considerations*

The research proposal was sent to the Institutional Review Board (IRB) for ethical valuation of the research design. Formal consent was sent to the participant’s parents or guardians, detailing the reason for the research, the methodology to be used, confidentiality and privacy guidelines and the duration of the study. The students were briefed about the study and given the freedom to choose whether or not to participate in the study. The students were assured confidentiality of any information gathered during the research period. Academic integrity was maintained throughout the study.

III. RESULTS

➤ *“Nearpod” and Students' Performance*

Although 30 students were recruited for the research, only 23 students participated in the pre-tests. The mean number of students who gave a correct answer per question ranged from 34.78% to 65.22%, with an average of 47.28% (Table 2).

Table 2: The Pre-test scores for 23 students. Column 2 indicates the number of students who correctly responded to

the question in column 1. Column 3 is a percentage of the number of students who gave correct responses

Question NO.	Pre- Test	Percentage of Correct Responses
1	11	47.83%
2	11	47.83%
3	9	39.13%
4	8	34.78%
5	11	47.83%
6	14	60.87%
7	8	34.78%
8	15	65.22%
Average	10.875	47.28%

The number of students willing to participate in the test increased from 23 to 24 during the post-intervention assessment. Similarly, there was a notable improvement in the number of students who reported correct answers per question, which translated to an increase in overall score from 47.28% to 55.13 % (Table 3). In addition, no negative change was noted between the pre-tests and post-test results per question, apart from the 6.16% declined score in question five and the 15.22% decline in question eight (Table 4)

Table 3: The Post-test scores for 23 students. Column 2 indicates the number of students correctly responding to the question in column 1. Column 3 is a percentage of the number of students who gave correct responses

Question NO.	Pre- Test	Percentage of Correct Responses
1	14	58.33%
2	13	54.17%
3	11	45.83%
4	13	54.17%
5	10	41.67%
6	17	70.83%
7	12	50.00%
8	12	50.00%
Average	12.75	53.13%

The added-value analysis indicated a significant improvement in 6 out of 8 questions, with a declined score in only questions. A significant improvement was noted on questions 4 and 7, with added values of 19.38% and 15.22%, respectively (Table 4). Overall, the added values after the “Nearpod” intervention increased by 5.85%, suggesting that the method effectively improves student scores.

Table 4 Summarizes the pre-and Post-test scores and change in added value (Last column).

Question NO.	Pre-Test	Percentage of correct responses	Post-test	Percentage of Correct Responses	Added value
1	11	47.83	14	58.33	10.51

2	11	47.83	13	54.17	6.34
3	9	39.13	11	45.83	6.70
4	8	34.78	13	54.17	19.38
5	11	47.83	10	41.67	-6.16
6	14	60.87	17	70.83	9.96
7	8	34.78	12	50.00	15.22
8	15	65.22	12	50.00	-15.22
Average	10.875	47.28	12.75	53.13	5.85

➤ *“Nearpod” and Student Satisfaction*

The student’s confidence in answering the questions varied from question to question (Figure 2). However, in all the questions, the study reported a significant improvement in perception and satisfaction, which could have positively impacted performance.

Fig 2: The variations in student’s perception and satisfaction per question. Overall, the satisfaction levels decreased from the first to the eighth question.

For the first question (in the questionnaire), 19 students found it easy to open the link to use the Nearpod, while 5 students were neutral. No student reported any challenges in using the technology. Additionally, 18 students were satisfied with the questions and the technology, while 3 were neutral, and just 3 were unsatisfied. For the third question, 12 students believed the system was important, while 9 were neutral, and just one disagreed. When we asked about self-learning management, 18 students found it positively differentiated students' level, while 6 were neutral, with no disagreement. For the fifth question about whether Nearpod looked appealing, 20 students found it attractive, while 2 were neutral and 2 disagreed. Besides this, 19 students believed that Nearpod improved self-learning, while five were neutral about this. When asked if they wanted to use Nearpod in all science classes, 20 students were happy and willing to use it, while 3 were neutral, and just one was not ready to use it. More interestingly, 18 students agreed on the importance of using the technology, 5 were neutral, and only one disagreed. Overall, 75% of the students either strongly agreed or agreed with using the technology, 20% were neutral, and only 5% disagreed on its importance (Table 5).

Table 5: Analysis of the student survey indicating the percentage of satisfaction per question.

Question	Totally agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Totally Disagree
1	15	4	5	0	0
2	5	13	3	2	1
3	9	3	11	0	1
4	6	12	6	0	0
5	11	9	2	1	1
6	9	10	5	0	0
7	9	9	5	0	1
8	10	10	3	0	1
Total	74	70	40	3	5
Percentage	39%	36%	20%	2%	3%

➤ *Student Perception of Using Nearpod*

The interview administered by the science teacher evaluated the student’s perception of using Nearpod to learn science concepts. All the 23 students who participated in the pre-test participated in the interview. They responded to all the questions as asked, and consistency in most questions was

observed. The analysis of the audio transcript and interview notes revealed two main themes that aligned with the research questions. There are; “Nearpod can help improve academic performance” and “Nearpod enhances peer interaction and student-teacher interactions”.

IV. DISCUSSION

This study utilized method design, which is proven effective in collecting more detailed information on a topic (Almaki, 2016). The qualitative phase of the research revealed significant improvement in science performance after the Nearpod intervention. Other studies have also reported similar findings using different populations. For example, Messina et al. reported significant improvement in the academic performance of dental students when Zoom lectures were combined with Nearpod review sessions (Messina et al., 2022).

The main reason for the increased performance was associated with the ability of the tool to promote active learning (Hakimi, 2020). In a study done in the UAE, the researchers noted that other reasons for improved performance were Nearpod's positive response and instant feedback to students (which was reported by 90% of the participants) and good interactivity (83.4%) (Alawadhi & Thabet, 2023). Abdullah et al. also cited student engagement and instructiveness as contributing to improved performance (Abdullah et al., 2019). In addition, using elementary students, Yanuarta et al. (2023) recorded a significant improvement in science studies. The researchers focused on one topic, a model that was also replicated in this study. This study also reported similar findings, with a significant improvement in students reporting positive answers per question. The findings, therefore, show that the impact of Nearpod on academic performance is not age or institutional-dependent. Nearpod's academic improvement is an overall effect noted in all learning institutions, from elementary to higher learning institutions.

Research has proven that student-instructor engagement is one factor that influences academic performance (Ong & Quek, 2023). The online learning environments introduced during the COVID-19 pandemic impeded this interaction; therefore, most students could not seek assistance from their instructors. The reduced interaction affected most students psychologically, which affected their performance (Xiao et al., 2023; Sun et al., 2022). Unlike most platforms used for online learning, researchers have shown that Nearpod enables students to freely interact with their teachers, replicating a class-like environment. Additionally, the student-student interaction using Nearpod significantly improved the quality of learning environments and the student's academic performance (Miao et al., 2022; Miao & Ma, 2022).

Students have mixed feelings about the importance of online learning and the effectiveness of the available online learning platforms. Overall, students believed that the online environment offered better access to learning resources, encouraged students to learn at their pace, enabled them to select their preferred learning environment and allowed them to stay at home (Bączek et al., 2021). On the other hand, complaints were raised about challenges using technological

devices and poor interactions, which negatively affected the student's perception of the learning environment (Saurabh et al., 2021). Worse, some researchers reported that more than 75.8% of students had not used any E-learning platform, and only 68.2% had average to good IT skills (Maqbool et al., 2022). All these negative issues negatively influenced the student's perception of online.

Contrary to these findings, this study revealed that Nearpod improved student's perception of online learning. Similar findings were reported by Alawadhi and Thabet (2021), who noted that the platform promoted fun learning and promoted online enjoyment. Further, Maclean and Crowe initially echoed the impact of good engagement and interaction in the online platform on student's perceptions (McClellan & Crowe, 2017). Therefore, regardless of the challenges the students experienced during the pandemic, those who could use the platform better perceived online learning.

Besides echoing the impact of Nearpod on academic performance, the thematic analysis also revealed the contribution of the platform in improving teaching abilities. The science teachers reported that the platform enabled them to effectively interact with their students and easily convey their information. In addition, other studies have shown that the ability of the platform to provide real-time data on course progress was a major boost to teaching (Perez, 2017). Additionally, the platform encourages a genre-based approach to learning and contains reading lessons for students with reading challenges (Pupah & Sholihah, 2022; Delacruz, 2014). As such, the platform was not only beneficial to the students but also eased teaching and reduced instructor workload.

➤ *Limitations of the Study*

The study was done within a short time frame and included participants from only one government school. Additionally, the study focused on grade nine students leaving other middle school and high school learning categories. Therefore, future studies should consider using longer research durations, including students from other educational levels and students from different learning institutions. Furthermore, assessing student progress over a long learning duration compared to those using a different platform will give a better glimpse of the impact of Nearpod on the learning process.

V. CONCLUSION

Nearpod is a valuable online learning tool that can teach science concepts to grade nine students. Its effectiveness is linked to its better student-student and student-teacher interactions and better student responses. In addition, the study has shown that Nearpod improved student perception of online learning. In the strive to introduce online, distanced and blended learning models, learning institutions should consider Nearpod as a learning tool.

➤ Conflict of Interest

The authors have no relevant non-financial or financial interests to disclose. The authors certify that they have no affiliation with any tool or organization mentioned in the subject matter of this study. Also, the authors have no proprietary or financial interest in the topic or tools discussed herein.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Gratitude to the University of Qatar for allowing us to research the topic of interest. We are also grateful to our supervisors, Dr. Norma Ghamrawi from the University of Qatar, for assistance throughout the research and to the principal and board of the government institution used for this research for granting the audience an opportunity to explore this topic in their institution.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Abdullah, A., Yahaya, M. F., & Mat Isa, N. (2020). The Impact of Nearpod Interactive Learning Platform in Quality Accounting Education for Sustainable Development. In *Charting a Sustainable Future of ASEAN in Business and Social Sciences: Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on the Future of ASEAN (ICoFA) 2019—Volume 1*.
- [2]. Alawadhi, A., & Thabet, R. A. (2023, May). Using Nearpod to Promote Engagement in Online ESL Classes: A Mixed-Methods Study in the Context of Higher Education. In *BUI D Doctoral Research Conference 2022: Multidisciplinary Studies*.
- [3]. Almalki, S. (2016). Integrating Quantitative and Qualitative Data in Mixed Methods Research--Challenges and Benefits. *Journal of education and learning*, 5(3), 288-296.
- [4]. Bączek, M., Zagańczyk-Bączek, M., Szpringer, M., Jaroszyński, A., & Woźakowska-Kapłon, B. (2021). Students' perception of online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic: a survey study of Polish medical students. *Medicine*, 100(7).
- [5]. Chaaban, Y., Arar, K., Sawalhi, R., Alhouti, I., & Zohri, A. (2021). Exploring teachers' professional agency within shifting educational contexts: A comparative study of Lebanon, Qatar, Kuwait, and Morocco. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 106, 103451.
- [6]. Delacruz, S. (2014). Using Nearpod in elementary guided reading groups. *TechTrends*, 58, 62-69.
- [7]. Hakami, M. (2020). Using Nearpod as a tool to promote active learning in higher education in a BYOD learning environment. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 9(1), 119-126.
- [8]. Li, X., & Pei, Z. (2023). Improving effectiveness of online learning for higher education students during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 1111028.
- [9]. Maqbool, S., Farhan, M., Safian, H. A., Zulqarnain, I., Asif, H., Noor, Z., ... & Rehman, M. E. U. (2022). Student's perception of E-learning during COVID-19 pandemic and its positive and negative learning outcomes among medical students: A country-wise study conducted in Pakistan and Iran. *Annals of Medicine and Surgery*, 82, 104713.
- [10]. McClean, S., & Crowe, W. (2017). Making room for interactivity: using the cloud-based audience response system Nearpod to enhance engagement in lectures. *FEMS microbiology letters*, 364(6), fnx052.
- [11]. Messina, D. M., Mikhail, S. S., Messina, M. J., & Novopoltseva, I. A. (2022). Assessment of learning outcomes of first year dental students using an interactive Nearpod educational platform. *Journal of Dental Education*, 86(7), 893-899.
- [12]. Miao, J., & Ma, L. (2022). Students' online interaction, self-regulation, and learning engagement in higher education: The importance of social presence to online learning. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 815220.
- [13]. Miao, J., Chang, J., & Ma, L. (2022). Teacher–student interaction, student–student interaction and social presence: their impacts on learning engagement in online learning environments. *The Journal of Genetic Psychology*, 183(6), 514-526.
- [14]. Ong, S. G. T., & Quek, G. C. L. (2023). Enhancing teacher–student interactions and student online engagement in an online learning environment. *Learning Environments Research*, 1-27.
- [15]. Perez, J. E. (2017). Nearpod. *Journal of the Medical Library Association: JMLA*, 105(1), 108..
- [16]. Pupah, E. M., & Sholihah, U. (2022). Enhancing EFL students' reading learning process in COVID-19 pandemic through Nearpod. *Englisia: Journal of Language, Education, and Humanities*, 9(2), 17-31.
- [17]. Saurabh, M. K., Patel, T., Bhabhor, P., Patel, P., & Kumar, S. (2021). Students' perception on online teaching and learning during COVID-19 pandemic in medical education. *Maedica*, 16(3), 439.
- [18]. Sun, H. L., Sun, T., Sha, F. Y., Gu, X. Y., Hou, X. R., Zhu, F. Y., & Fang, P. T. (2022). The influence of teacher–student interaction on the effects of online learning: Based on a serial mediating model. *Frontiers in psychology*, 13, 779217.
- [19]. Taherdoost, H. (2016). Sampling methods in research methodology; how to choose a sampling technique for research. *How to choose a sampling technique for research*.
- [20]. UNESCO. (2020) *Policy brief: Education during COVID-19 and beyond*. https://www.un.org/development/desa/dspd/wp-content/uploads/sites/22/2020/08/sg_policy_brief_covid19_and_education_august_2020.pdf.

- [21]. Wong, K. (2014). Paradigms and Methodologies. *vue* 2014 EDITORIAL , 4.
- [22]. Xiao, M., Tian, Z., & Xu, W. (2023). Impact of teacher-student interaction on students' classroom well-being under online education environment. *Education and Information Technologies*, 1-23.
- [23]. Yanuarto, W. N., Setyaningsih, E., & Amri, K. (2023). Employing Nearpod as a Resource to Encourage Active Students in BYOD Mathematics Learning Model. *JTAM (Jurnal Teori dan Aplikasi Matematika)*, 7(1), 174-184.
- [24]. Zheng, M., Bender, D., & Lyon, C. (2021). Online learning during COVID-19 produced equivalent or better student course performance as compared with pre-pandemic: empirical evidence from a school-wide comparative study. *BMC medical education*, 21, 1-11.